

**AN
INTERNSHIP REPORT
ON
DIGITAL WATERMARKING SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT
BY
KAMAL ACHARYA
(Tribhuvan University)**

Date: 2025/06/26

- TABLE OF CONTENTS -

1. Introduction

- 1.1 Synopsis ...
- Scope & Objectives ...
- Overview ...

2. General Description

- 2.1 About Steganography ...
- 2.2 User characteristics ...

3. System Analysis & Design

- 3.1 Software Requirements Specifications ...
- 3.2 User Requirements ...
- 3.3 Problem Definition ...
- 3.4 Solution Provided ...

4. System Planning

- 4.1 Selection of Technology ...
- 4.2 Development of Modules ...
- 4.3 Cost Estimation ...
- 4.4 Schedule Estimation ...

5 System Life Cycle

- 5.1 Description
 - 5.1.1 Context Diagram ...
 - 5.1.2 Flow Chart ...
 - 5.1.3 Use Case Diagram ...
 - 5.1.4 Class Diagram ...
- 5.2 Diagrams
 - 5.2.1 Context Diagram ...
 - 5.2.2 Flow Chart ...
 - 5.2.3 Use Case Diagram ...
 - 5.2.4 Class Diagram ...

6. System Implementation

6.1 Software Development Lifecycle ...

6.2 Hardware Specification ...

6.3 Software Specification ...

7. Cost Benefit Analysis ...

8. Coding...

9. Testing

9.1 Levels of testing

9.2 Test Plan & Test Case Specification ...

10. User Manual

10.1 Screen Layout ...

10.2 Operational Manual ...

11. Annexure

11.1 Limitations of the Project ...

11.2 Future Enhancements ...

12. Bibliography ...

1. Introduction

1.1 Synopsis

Data security is the essential in the today's world of internet and networking. In any organization information is critical. In today's world people are ready to spent thousands and lacks of money in order to ensure high level of information security. In spite of spending such a huge amount, still the objective of securing the information is not achieved as the data some how gets in the hands of hacker. As the technology for securing the data is advancing, hackers are also keeping pace with this technology. Hackers now make use of certain algorithm or other techniques to decode the data encoded by the senders. One of the ways to ensure security is to ensure that data is not visible to the hacker. This can be done by hiding the message itself behind some other objects. Here we are achieving this data security concept through the technique of Steganography.

1.2 Objective and scope of the project

Objective:

The main objective for developing this application is that, it can provide the user with security of data. It will also provide the transfer of data from one machine to another in from of files. Only the authorized user and administrator can access the application.

Scope:

The project 'Steganography' will basically deal with data security. It will provide security of data by mechanism which is popularly known as 'Steganography' in the world of internet security.

In this project, the focus is on image watermarking **visible** as well as **invisible**.

Visible Watermarking involves only insertion of the watermark. Whereas Invisible Watermarking involves insertion of the watermark and extraction of a Watermark.

- It will embed any text data into any other suitable file such as image, audio, video, text file, without actually changing the content of the carrier file.
- It will also allow user to transfer the file containing the information to other machine through LAN.
- Consequently will also retrieve the information from file in which information is embedded.
- It will also provide a mechanism for embedding a whole text file in other files.
- It will provide the mechanism to retrieve the text file as it was embedded without changing the format or look of the file in which it was embedded.

1.3 Overview

This project will basically implement the Steganographic technique of hiding the data or information behind the image/audio/video file. It will also help in the transfer of the information from one machine to another machine. The main aim of this project will be the data security aspect.

2. General Description

2.1 History of Watermarking:

Watermarks are identification marks produced during the paper making process. The first watermarks appeared in Italy during the 13th century, but their use rapidly spread across Europe. They were used as a means to identify the papermaker or the trade guild that manufactured the paper. The marks shown here were created by a wire sewn onto the paper mold. Watermarks continue to be used today as manufacturer's marks and to prevent forgery.

The first marks were simple objects.

This mark is the source of the term "foolscap" for a certain size of paper.

During the Seventeenth and Eighteenth Centuries, British papermakers began to use certain symbols to designate the paper's intended size. According to Dard Hunter, it would not be reasonable to assume that prior to that time the different watermarks would have denoted the various sizes of paper, because every different size of paper would have required a special pair of moulds. Marks such as the foolscap, hand, post and pott came into use in the 1400s (for example, the 'foolscap' mark can be traced to the year 1479).

This first watermark to be utilized in the making of paper in the colonies stood for the partnership that Rittenhouse entered into with William Bradford, the first printer in the Province of Pennsylvania and two other gentlemen. In 1704, Bradford dropped out of the partnership, and two years later Rittenhouse became the sole owner of the papermill. After 1706 Rittenhouse employed two watermarks, the one being just the letters "W" and "R" joined together, and the other being the image of a clover leaf inside a crowned shield with the word "Pensilvania" below it. The initial letters watermark was positioned on one half of the sheet of paper, while the other watermark was positioned on the opposite half of the sheet.

In 1790 an Englishman by the name of John Phipps patented a method of teaching writing in which ruled lines were embedded in the paper by means of watermarking. The nearly invisible lines would help pupils to write straighter and more uniformly.

The next major step in the history of watermarks came in the late Eighteenth and early Nineteenth Centuries with the introduction of finer mesh brass screens. The finer mesh allowed more detail to be captured when a shape was pressed into it. And that is exactly what papermakers began to do. They continued to shape and bend wire to form images, but instead of attaching the shaped wire to the screen, they pressed the shaped wire into the screen itself.

Digital watermarking is a technique which allows an individual to add hidden copyright notices or other verification messages to digital audio, video, or image signals and documents. Such a message is a group of bits describing information pertaining to the signal or to the author of the signal (name, place, etc.). The technique takes its name from watermarking of paper or money as a security measure. Digital watermarking can be a form of steganography, in which data is hidden in the message without the end user's knowledge.

A simple example of a digital watermark would be a visible "seal" placed over an image to identify the copyright. However the watermark might contain additional information including the identity of the purchaser of a particular copy of the material. According to the human perception, **the digital watermarks can be divided into two different types as follows: visible and invisible.** Visible watermark is a secondary translucent overlaid into the primary image as shown in the figure

2.2 Problem Definition:

Digital watermarking is the process of inserting a digital signal or pattern into digital content. The signal, known as a watermark, can be used to identify the owner of the work, to authenticate the content, and to trace

illegal copies of the work. A watermark is a form, image or text that is impressed onto paper, which provides evidence of its authenticity. Digital watermarking is an extension of this concept in the digital world.

Techniques that use to watermark a digital image is LSB (Least Significant Bit) Algorithm. The system implements both visible as well as invisible watermarking. The digital content could be a still image, an audio clip, video clip, a text document, or some form of digital data that the creator or owner would like to protect.

The main purpose of the watermark is to identify who the owner of the digital data is, but it can also identify the intended recipient. This project focuses on still digital image watermarking.

2.3 Applications of Digital Watermarking:

Very frequently there's a need to associate some additional information with a digital content, such as music, image or video. For example, copyright notice may need to be associated with an image to identify a legal owner of that image. Or a serial number may need to be associated with a video to identify a legitimate user of that video. Or some kind of identifier may need to be associated with a song to help find a database

where more information about it can be obtained from. This additional information can be associated with a digital content by placing it in the header of a digital file, or for images, it can be encoded as a visible notice. Storing information in the header of a digital file has a couple of disadvantages. First, it may not survive a file format conversion, and second, once an image is displayed or printed, its association with the header file and information stored in it is lost. Adding a visible notice to an image may not be acceptable if it negatively affects the esthetics of the image. This could be corrected to some extent by making the notice as small as possible and/or moving it to a visually insignificant portion of the image, such as the edge. However, once on the edge, this additional information can easily be cropped off, either intentionally or unintentionally.

The Lena image used as a test image on the left, and the cropped part of the original image which identifies the copyright owner, Playboy Enterprises, Inc. on the right. This is exactly what happened with an image of Lena Soderberg after its copyright notice was cropped off. The image was originally published as a Playboy centerfold in November 1972. After the image has been scanned for use as the test image, most of it has been cropped including the copyright notice which was printed on the edge of the image. The “Lena” image became probably the most frequently used test image in image processing research, and appeared in a number of journal articles without any reference to its rightful owner, Playboy Enterprises, Inc. Digital watermarking seems to be the suitable method for associating this additional information, the metadata, with a digital work. The metadata is imperceptibly embedded as a watermark in a digital content, the cover work, and it becomes inseparable from it. Furthermore, since watermarks will go through the same transformations as the cover work they are embedded in, it is sometimes possible to learn whether and how the content has been tampered with by looking into the resulting watermarks.

2.4 Classification of Digital Watermarking Applications:

There are a number of different watermarking application scenarios, and they can be classified in a number of different ways. The following classification is based on the type of information conveyed by the watermark. In the following section we’ll provide a more detailed explanation of possible application scenarios involving watermarking.

- **Digital Watermarking for Copyright Protection:**

Copyright protection appears to be one of the first applications digital watermarking was targeted for. The metadata in this case contains information about the copyright owner. It is imperceptibly embedded as a watermark in the cover work to be protected. If users of digital content (music, images, and video) have an easy access to watermark detectors, they should be able to recognize and interpret the embedded watermark and identify the copyright owner of the watermarked content.

An example of one commercial application created for that purpose is Digimarc Corporation ImageBridge Solution. The ImageBridge watermark detector is made available in a form of plug-ins for many popular image processing solutions, such as Adobe PhotoShop or Corel PhotoPaint. When a user opens an image using Digimarc

enabled application, Digimarc's watermark detector will recognize a watermark. It will then contact a remote database using the watermark as a key to find a copyright owner and his contact information. An honest user can use that information to contact the copyright owner to request permission to use the image. We have shown above how an invisibly embedded watermark can be used to identify copyright ownership. It would be nice if an embedded watermark could be used to prove the ownership as well, perhaps even in a court of law. We can envision the following scenario: A copyright owner distributes his/her digital content with his/her invisible watermark embedded in it. In the case of a copyright ownership dispute, a legal owner should be able to prove his ownership by demonstrating that he owns the original work, and that the disputed work has been derived from the original by embedding a watermark into it. This could be done by producing the original work together with the watermark detector, and having detector detect the owner's watermark in a disputed work. Unfortunately, it appears that the above scenario can be defeated under certain

assumptions, and because of that watermarking has not been accepted yet as a technology dependable enough to be used to prove the ownership. One potential problem is related to the availability of watermark detector. It has been demonstrated that if a detector is widely available, then it is not possible to protect watermark security. In other words, if a detector is available, it is always possible to remove an embedded watermark. This can be achieved by repeatedly making imperceptible changes to the watermarked work, until a watermark detector fails to detect the watermark. Once the watermark is removed, the original owner will not be able to prove his ownership any longer. Even if the original watermark cannot be removed, Craver et al. Under certain conditions, it is possible to add another watermark to an already watermarked image in such a way as to make it appear that this second watermark is present in all copies of disputed image, including the original image. This is known as an ambiguity attack, and it could be used not only to dispute the ownership claims of the rightful copyright owner, but also to make new ownership claim to the original digital content.

- **Digital Watermarking for Copy Protection:**

The objective of a copy protection application is to control access to and prevent illegal copying of copyrighted content. It is an important application, especially for digital content, because digital copies can be easily made, they are perfect reproductions of the original, and they can easily and inexpensively be distributed over the Internet with no quality degradation. There are a number of technical and legal issues that need to be addressed and resolved in order to create a working copy protection solution. Those issues are difficult to resolve in open systems, and we are not aware of the existence of an open system copy protection solution. Copy protection is feasible in closed, proprietary systems, and we will describe one proprietary solution, the Digital Versatile Disk (DVD) copy

It is obvious that this copy control mechanism will work only if every DVD recorder contains a watermark detector. The problem is how to ensure that every DVD recorder will have the watermark detector, since there does not seem to exist a natural economic incentive for DVD manufacturers to increase a production cost of their product by incorporating watermark detectors in DVD recorders. After all, a perceived market

value of a DVD recorder with a watermark detector may be lower compared with a recorder without it, because a customer would rather have a device that can make illegal copies.

One solution to this problem could be to force DVD manufacturers to add watermark detectors in their devices by law. Since such a law does not exist, and even if it did, it would be very difficult to enforce it across every country in the world, an alternative solution was needed. The solution that has been adopted for DVD systems is based on the patent license. Basically, the DVD encryption patent license makes it mandatory to use watermark detectors in the patent compliant devices.

The patent- license approach ensures that compliant devices will use watermark detectors and prevent illegal copying, but it also makes it legal to manufacture noncompliant devices, the devices which do not implement the patented decryption, and therefore do not have to implement a watermark detector. Consequently, the DVD copy control mechanism does not prevent all possible illegal copying.

Interaction of encryption and copy control, combined with the playback control, a mechanism which allows a DVD compliant device to detect illegal copies, is used to create a solution where only illegal copies can be played on noncompliant devices, and only legal copies can be played on compliant devices. The objective of this scheme is to insure that one device will not be able to play both legal and illegal content. If a customer wants to play both legal and illegal copies he will have to purchase both compliant and noncompliant devices. However, if one of the two has to be selected, the hope is that most customers will choose a compliant one.

- **Digital Watermarking for Fingerprinting:**

There are some applications where the additional information associated with a digital content should contain information about the end user, rather than about the owner of a digital content. For example, consider what happens in a film making environment. During the course of film production, the incremental results of work are usually distributed each day to a number of people involved in a movie making activity. Those distributions are known as film dailies, and they are confidential. If a version is leaked out, the studio would like to be able to identify the source of the leak. The problem of identifying the source of a leak can be solved by distributing slightly different copies to each recipient, thus uniquely associating each copy with a person receiving it.

As another example, consider a digital cinema environment, an environment where films are distributed to cinemas in digital format instead of via express mail in the form of celluloid prints. Even though digital distribution of films could be more flexible and efficient and less expensive, film producers and distributors are slow to adopt it because they are concerned about potential loss of revenue caused by illegal copying and redistribution of films. Now, if each cinema receives a uniquely identifiable copy of a film, then, if illegal copies have been made, it should be possible to associate those copies with the cinema where they have been made, and initiate an appropriate legal action against it.

Associating unique information about each distributed copy of digital content is called fingerprinting, and watermarking is an appropriate solution for that application because it is invisible and inseparable from the content. This type of application is also

known as traitor tracing because it is useful for monitoring or tracing illegally produced copies of digital work. Also, since watermarking can be used to keep track of multiple transactions that have taken place in the history of the copy of a digital content, the term transaction tracking has been used as well.

- **Digital Watermarking for Content Authentication:**

Multimedia editing software makes it easy to alter digital content. For example, The left one is the original, authentic image. The middle one is the modified version of the original image, and the right one shows the image region which has been tampered. Since it is so easy to interfere with a digital content, there's a need to be able to verify integrity and authenticity of the content.

A solution to this problem could be borrowed from cryptography, where digital signature has been studied as a message authentication method. Digital signature essentially represents some kind of summary of the content. If any part of the content is modified, its summary, the signature, will change making it possible to detect that some kind of tampering has taken place. One example of digital signature technology being used for image authentication is the trustworthy digital camera.

Digital signature information needs to be somehow associated and transmitted with a digital content it was created from. Watermarks can obviously be used to achieve that association by embedding signature directly into the content. Since watermarks used in the content authentication applications have to be designed to become invalid if even slight modifications of digital content take place, they are called fragile watermarks.

Fragile watermarks, therefore, can be used to confirm authenticity of a digital content. They can also be used in applications where it is important to figure out how digital content was modified or which portion of it has been tampered with. For digital images, this can be done by dividing an image into a number of blocks and creating and embedding a fragile watermark into each and every block.

Digital content may undergo lossy compression transformation, such as JPEG image conversion. While resulting JPEG compressed image still has an authentic content, the image authenticity test based on the fragile watermark described above will fail. Semifragile watermarks can be used instead. They are designed to survive standard transformations, such as lossy compression, but they will become invalid if a major change, takes place.

- **Digital Watermarking for Broadcast Monitoring:**

Many valuable products are regularly broadcast over the television network: news, movies, sports events, advertisements, etc. Broadcast time is very expensive, and advertisers may pay hundreds of thousands of dollars for each run of their short commercial that appears during commercial breaks of important movies, series or sporting events. The ability to bill accurately in this environment is very important. It is important to advertisers who would like to make sure that they will pay only for the

commercials which were actually broadcast. And, it is important for the performers in those commercials who would like to collect accurate royalty payments from advertisers.

Broadcast monitoring is usually used to collect information about the content being broadcast, and this information is then used as the bases for billing as well as other purposes. A simple way to do monitoring is to have human observers watch the broadcast and keep track of everything they see. This kind of broadcast monitoring is expensive, and it is prone to errors. Automated monitoring is clearly better. There are two categories of automated monitoring systems: passive and active. Passive monitoring systems monitor the content being broadcast and make an attempt to recognize it by comparing it with the known content stored in a database. They are difficult to implement for a couple of reasons. It is difficult to compare broadcast signals against the database content, and it is expensive to maintain and manage a large database of content to compare against.

Active monitoring systems rely on the additional information which identifies the content and gets broadcast together with the content itself. For analog television broadcast, this content identification information can be encoded in the vertical blanking interval (VBI) of the video signal. The problem with this approach is that it is suitable for analog transmission only, and even in that case it may not be reliable because, in the USA, content distributors do not have to distribute information embedded in the VBI.

A more appropriate solution for active monitoring is based on watermarking. The watermark containing broadcast identification information gets embedded into the content itself, and the resulting broadcast monitoring solution becomes compatible with broadcast equipment for both digital and analog transmission.

- **Digital Watermarking for System Enhancement:**

Digital watermarking can also be used to convey side-channel information with the purpose of enhancing functionality of the system or adding value to the content it is embedded in. This type of applications, where a device is designed to react to watermark for the benefit of the user, is also referred to as device control applications.

An example of an early application of watermarking for system enhancement is described in the Ray Dolby's patent application filed in 1981, where he proposed to make radio devices which would turn Dolby FM noise reduction control system on and off automatically, in response to an inaudible signal broadcast within the audio frequency spectrum. Such a signal constitutes a simple watermark, and the proposed radio device was an enhancement compared to the radio devices used at that time, where listeners had to manually turn their radio's Dolby FM decoder on and off.

More recently, Philips and Microsoft have demonstrated an audio watermarking system for music. Basically, as music is played, a microphone on a PDA can capture and digitize the signal, extract the embedded watermark and based on information encoded in it, identify the song. If a PDA is network connected, the system can link to a database and provide some additional information about the song, including information about how to purchase it.

Another example of a similar application is Digimarc MediaBridge system. On content production side, watermarks representing unique identifiers are embedded into images, and then printed and distributed in magazines as advertisements. On the user side, an image from a magazine is scanned, the watermark is extracted using the

MediaBridge software, and the unique identifier is used to direct a web browser to an associated website.

Visible watermarks can be used in following cases:

- Visible watermarking for enhanced copyright protection.

In such situations, where images are made available through Internet and the content owner is concerned that the images will be used commercially (e.g. imprinting coffee mugs) without payment of royalties. Here the content owner desires an ownership mark, that is visually apparent, but which does not prevent image being used for other purposes (e.g. scholarly research).

- Visible watermarking used to indicate ownership originals.

In this case images are made available through the Internet and the content owner desires to indicate the ownership of the underlying materials (library manuscript), so an observer might be encouraged to patronize the institutions that own the material.

Invisible watermarks do not change the signal to a perceptually great extent, i.e., there are only minor variations in the output signal. An example of an invisible watermark is when some bits are added to an image modifying only its least significant bit. Invisible watermarks that are unknown to the end user are steganography. While the addition of the hidden message to the signal does not restrict that signal's use, it provides a mechanism to track the signal to the original owner.

- To protect digital media by fingerprinting.

Another application is to protect digital media by fingerprinting each copy with the purchaser's information. If the purchaser makes illegitimate copies, these will contain his name. Fingerprints are an extension to watermarking principle and can be both visible and invisible.

- Copyright protection

This is the most prominent application of Digital watermarking. It embeds the information about the owner to prevent others from claiming copyright. It Requires very high level of robustness.

- Copy protection

It embeds watermark to disallow unauthorized copying of the cover. For example, compliant DVD players will not playback or copy data that carries a “copy never” watermark.

- Content Authentication

It embeds a watermark to detect modifications to the cover. The watermark in this case has low robustness, “fragile”.

- Transaction Tracking

It embeds a watermark to convey information about the legal recipient of the cover.

This is useful to monitor or trace back illegally produced copies of the cover. This is usually referred to as “fingerprinting”.

- Broadcast Monitoring

It embeds a watermark in the cover and use automatic monitoring to verify whether cover was broadcasted as agreed requirements.

2.4 About Steganography

Steganography is a technology that hides a message within an object, a text, or a picture. It is often confused with cryptography, not in name but in appearance and usage. The easiest way to differentiate the two is to remember Steganography conceals not only the contents of the message but also the mere existence of a message. Steganography is a Greek word meaning covered writing, which is as old as cryptography itself and can be as simple as writing with invisible ink made from vinegar or lemon juice. Computerized applications of Steganography have truly breathtaking implications, including hiding large data files inside digital graphic or audio files or even on ordinary- looking and sounding CD-ROMs and digital audio tapes.

The first steganographic technique was developed in ancient Greece around 440 B.C... Herodotus’s Histories describes two types of the earliest steganography. The first type involved the shaving of a slave’s head, and then a tattoo was inscribed on the scalp. When the slave’s hair had grown back and hidden the message, the slave was sent to warn of the Persians’ impending invasion. The recipient once again shaved the slave’s head and retrieved the important warning. Another method was to modify ancient writing tablets. The layer of wax covering the tablets was the surface upon which messages were written. However Demeratus, a Greek exiled into Persia, devised a plan to hide a message by removing the layer of wax and writing directly on the underlying wood a warning to Sparta that the Persians were planning an invasion. The tablets were then covered again with wax and appeared unused to the examiners of the shipment.

Firstly, one must understand the components of a steganographic message. The “secret message” refers to the part of the message which is intended to be hidden. The “cover data” refers to the container in which the secret message is hidden. The “stego message” refers to the final product. From a top-down approach there exist three types of steganographic approaches: pure, private key and public key steganography. These categories convey the level of security with which the stego message is embedded, transmitted and read. Pure steganography uses no keyed system to embed clear text or “null cipher” text into the cover data in order to hide the existence of a secret message. Pure steganography is the least secure method. It is only secure in two aspects which are, the fact only the sending and receiving parties know of the secret message’s existence and which steganographic algorithm was used to hide the message. In steganalysis, this type is the easiest to crack since once detected the message can only have been hidden in as many ways as the number of steganographic algorithms which exist. The foremost difficult aspect is in the detection effort. The difficulty lies in the fact that the vast majority of screened data do not include pre-modification copies of themselves. For

example, if the NSA were to screen thousands of web sites for steganographic material, most of the authors of this material would not leave the original copies of the cover data in the web site's directory or even on the computer which produced the stego message. Since in its simplest form, only the least significant bits of each byte representing a digital photo have been modified to carry the secret message, the message would be virtually undetectable given a correct $(\text{cover data size})/(\text{secret message size})$ ratio. However, once detected a pure stego message could be cracked with relative ease.

The private key method uses a mutual key for encrypting then hiding the secret message within the cover data. As in traditional encryption the private key system is only as robust as the knowledge of the key. Since the private key system requires both parties to know the key, once it is compromised the entire stego message is non-secure. Public key encrypted steganography uses the key pair system to add layer of robustness to the process. As in public key encryption, the public key of the recipient is used to encrypt the secret message and only that user's private key may decrypt it after extracting it from the cover data. This is the most secure type of steganography. This approach is recommended since it combines the benefits of hiding the existence of a secret message with the security of encryption.

Though they may not always be able to crack your code, those who monitor communications for a living can usually tell if a message has been encrypted using the DES, PGP, IDEA, RSA, or other standard cryptosystem. Unfortunately, in some circles, the very fact that you're sending a message encrypted makes you automatically suspect. What, after all, do you have to hide? Never mind that there's no such stigma attached to sending paper mail in envelopes. Certainly, in places where sending encrypted messages is clearly illegal, steganographic methods become essential.

Watermarking can be image, Video and Audio

Image

Video

Audio

Example of visible watermark :-

Original Image:

Watermark Image:

Image After Watermarking(With Various Compression Attacks)

Example of Invisible watermark :-

2.5 Image Formats:

There are many types of image formats, but with respect to our project we consider following three popular image formats:

- JPEG (Joint Photographic Experts Group)

Format name: JPEG (Joint Photographic Experts Group)

Extension: jpg, jpeg, jfif, jfl

Type: bitmapped

Compression algorithm: JPEG (lossy)

Color depth: 24 bits

Platforms: all

JPEG format was designed to transfer graphic data and images via digital telecommunication networking and was generally used to hold and transfer full color photo realistic images. Before JPEG, there were very few formats, which supported 24 bit halftone images. TIFF and BMP formats allowed holding 24 bit data, but they failed to perform a lossless compression of the data, which contained thousand colors from the real world,

Jpeg compresses photos though with quality loss. Compression algorithm is that data are deleted for deallocation (it allows to raise the compression degree). Data are hold as pixel block in a certain color with intensity information save (the matter is that a human eye discerns disintensity better than discoloration).

- Bitmap (Microsoft Windows Bitmap)

Format name: Bitmap (Microsoft Windows Bitmap)

Extension: bmp, dib, rle

Type: bitmapped

Compression algorithm: RLE (lossless), without compression

Color depth: up to 32 bits

Platforms: Windows, OS/2

Bitmap is a home Windows raster format, which is used practically for all possible raster data storage. All BMP versions were designed for computers with Intel processors. The current format version is device undependable (that means that Bitmap determines the pixel's color without reference to display device) and makes possible to record images of a different quality level (to the point of 32 bits). After revising, the format was used to hold color and black and white images, so it became general. The main advantage of the format is considered to be its usability and wide software support.

- PNG (Portable Network Graphic)

Format name: PNG (Portable Network Graphic)

Extension: png

Type: bitmapped

Compression algorithm: Deflate (lossless)

Color depth: up to 48 bits

Platforms: all

PNG file format is a comparatively new progressive format originally designed to replace dated Gif. PNG format has got a set of new features that Gif lacks. PNG also performs a lossless compression with the help of Deflate algorithm (read more about Deflate algorithm [here](#)) and supports interlaced mode. The format handles 256 transparency levels (that means that images might be partially transparent). The fact, that the format supports color depth up to 48 bits and performs a lossless compression, makes possible to hold photo realistic images. They won't lose its quality while compressing and decompressing. PNG format is used specially for networking.

2.6 User Characteristics

Data security and data transfer is the main functionality provided by this application. The user of this application needs to be conscious about the data security and its importance. However any user who is aware of or has basic knowledge of computer can use it. The user need to have little basic knowledge of what the Steganography is for using the data security functionality provided by this application. However this application can be independently be used for transferring the files from one machine to other machine. Thus if any user who is not concerned or aware about the data security part can utilize the data/file transfer capability of this application.

3. System Analysis and Design

3.1 SRS (Software Requirements Specifications)

SRS is a document that completely describes what the proposed software should do without describing how the software should do it. SRS describes the complete external behavior of the proposed software.

Title: Steganography

Aim: The main aim of this project or application is to provide high quality of data security and transfer of data from source to destination.

3.2 User Requirements

The software which will be developed should have the following capabilities:

- It should be capable of identifying the authorized and un-authorized users.
- It should be capable of embedding text message into image file, audio file and video file.
- Before embedding the message, the message should be first encrypted.
- On embedding the message, the format and look of the image, audio, video should not be distorted.
- Reverse to embedding the message, it should also retrieve the message from image/audio/video file as it was embedded.
- After embedding the message, it should retrieve the message from the file in the same format in which the message was previously embedded.
- It should also decrypt the message which was encrypted by the sender.
- After retrieving the message from the file, the look and the format of the image, audio, video should not change.
- It should be capable of embedding the whole text file into the image file, audio file and the video file, so that user could be able to embed large message in the form of text file.
- The format of data in file should not change during the process of transfer.
- When the file is embedded in the image file, audio, video the look of the file holding the file should not change.

- Before embedding the file, the data of the file should be encrypted.
- It should also decrypt the content of the file which was encrypted by the sender.
- After retrieving the file from the image, audio, video file which holds the message the format of the image, audio, video file should not change.
- There should be mechanism for alerting the receiver when any file is send to him.
- There should be mechanism for alerting the sender when any file is accepted by the receiver.
- There should be mechanism for alerting the sender if any file is rejected by the receiver.
- Since this software is responsible for the data security, the software should be safe enough that it does not get miss-used.

3.3 Problem statement

The problem statements are as follows:

- For some applications User-Id and password are not protected. As a result any one who is interested in using the application can access it.
- Sending a plain text of data to the receiver is not secure. Since the data is readable any one can get the information.
- Even if the message is encoded before sending the message, it can be decoded by the hacker by making use of certain algorithm.
- Some times the systems may not be connected properly. As a result the data which is transferred may not reach the destination in proper format.
- It is very difficult to maintain reliability of the software. The reliability comes with the cost.
- When the message falls in the hand of the hacker then the hacker can insert, delete or modify the content of the original message.
- Confidentiality of the message is lost if the message is not protected properly.
- A hacker can pose as sender and can misguide the receiver. Thus hacker can violate the authentication.

- In some cases hacker are not able to get the content of the original message. Thus they perform the exponential attack. Exponential attack is the attack where the hacker destroys the content of the original message.

3.4 Solution provided

- The software should be provided proper user id and password, so that no one can misuse it.
- The user id and the password should be protected from the internal and the external hacker.
- The message will be encoded using Steganography technique so that if it falls in the hand of the hacker then hacker will not be able to detect it.
- Since in Steganography technique the message is not visible the hacker gets fooled. Thus hacker can not make use of any kind of algorithm to get the original content of the message.
- Software will be reliable enough to handle exceptional conditions; it will provide operability on different platforms.
- In Stenography, as the message is not visible the hacker can not perform any kind of modification.
- Confidentiality level is very high in this technique.
- Authentication of the user can be done using user id and password. This ensures that interception is avoided.
- Receiver can easily rely on the Steganography.
- Steganography is the technique where sender can hide the original message behind the audio, video, text or image and send it to receiver. Receiver at opposite end can retrieve the message by using the same technique.

4. System Planning

System Planning is an important for any successful project. With out proper planning the project is doomed. Good planning can be done after the requirements for the project are available. The input to the project planning activity is the requirement specification. The output of this phase is the project plan, which is the document describing the different aspects of the plan. The project plan is instrumental in driving the development process through the remaining phases. The major issues the project plan addresses are:

- Selection of technology.
- Development of modules.
- Cost Estimation// still to include
- Average Duration Estimation //still to include
- Gantt Chart

Various models have been proposed for the software planning. E.g. COCOMO (COConstructive COSt MOdel) developed by Boehm. The model fits the large scale projects and can be implemented with few modifications for the small projects.

4.1 Selection of Technology

The system planning also includes the selection of technology for the development of the modules and the application. The technology which will be used in this project is JAVA and HTML. The JAVA technology will be used for providing platform independency to the application and for doing the bit level calculations in the modules. The HTML technology would be used for the development of help modules which will be meant for providing to the application.

The application which we will be developing is a stand alone application. This application, apart from providing data security communicates with other machines for file transfer. The machines which will be communicating might not have same platform. So the application needs to be platform independent. For embedding the files and the message the image, audio, video files need to be rendered at bit level. So a very secure technique is required for dealing at bit level.

System Development Model

This project deals with the secure transfer of data from one machine to another machine via LAN. The development of such software would really be complex task. It is more of a technical project. Although the requirements and the concepts of the project are clear at the initial stage but would require some advancement at the later stage. This advancement can not be detected initially. So it would be better to develop those modules that are clear at the current stage. As the development proceeds the further features can be

added into the system as per the requirement of the user. The project development also requires the coverage of technical risks.

Since the development of the system can be done and advanced features can be added at the regular interval of time, for this system *Incremental model* is recommended. In incremental model, iterative development can be done i.e. system can be developed in number of phases. First that module is developed whose requirement is clear. If the user is satisfied with that module then work is done on other iteration. Also incremental model helps us to cover risk for our project.

About Java

Java is an Object Oriented Programming language which can be used for developing platform independent applications. The platform independency means that the application developed on one platform can also be executed on other platforms. Also Java provides strong support for file handling mechanism. It has a very good exception handling mechanism which can be used for detecting the various file errors while performing operations on them. It has a wide range of bitwise operators for supporting operations at bit level. Java also has classes for socket programming which can be used for communication between the machines. Also object oriented techniques helps in development of applications which can be re-used. Java can also be linked with HTML for web based developments.

Reason for using Java & HTML

Following are the reasons for using the Java and Html:

- ✓ Java will help in doing the operations at the bit level in embedding the message/data file in the image/audio/video file.
- ✓ Since our application is standalone and need communication between different platform machines, Java can be used for platform independent application development.
- ✓ The Object-Oriented concept can be used for reusability of the application and is very good for Incremental Model of software development which we will be used.
- ✓ Java provides various streams for handling files; it also has classes rendering images.

4.2 Development of Modules

This project will contain mainly six major modules: User interface, Embed Module, Retrieve Module, Sender Module, Receiver Module and Help Module. First these modules will be developed independently and then this all will be integrate together.

1) User Interface Module (Steganograph):

This module will basically provide the main form for accessing the functionality of the application. Since the application will be implemented in the form of MDI parent child property for user interface, this module will work as a parent form for other child forms.

2) Embed Module :

This module will basically provide the functionality of embedding the message and the text or data file in the image, audio, video files. It will also have a sub module named “Encrypt” which will be responsible for encrypting the message and the data file. The embed module will make the use of this encrypt module for encryption purpose. This module will handle the backend task for Embed File form.

3) Retrieve Module:

This module will basically provide the functionality of retrieving the message and the text or data file from the image, audio, video files. It will also have a sub module named “Decrypt” which will be responsible for decrypting the message and the data file. The retrieve module will make the use of this decrypt module for decryption purpose. This module will handle the backend task for Retrieve File form.

4) Sender Module:

This module will basically provide the functionality of sending the files from one machine to another machine. This module will make use of socket programming for sending the file to other machines. This module will also provide the user interface that is child form (Send File).

5) Receiver Module:

This module will basically provide the functionality of receiving the files coming from other machines. This module will also make the use of socket programming for receiving the files from other machines. This module will not have any user interface. It will be functioning in the background.

6) Help Module:

This module will be responsible for providing the Help to the application. It will be implemented using JAVA and HTML both. The form for this module will be designed in JAVA, whereas the content for the help will be designed using HTML.

5. System Implementation

5.1 System Development Life Cycle:-

Preliminary Investigation:-

The First step is to identify a need for the new system. This will include determine whether a business problem or opportunity exists, conducting a feasibility study to determine if the proposed solution is cost effective, and developing a project plan. This process may involve end users who come up with an idea for improving their work. Ideally the process occurs in tandem with a view of the organization strategy.

System Requirements:-

Requirements analysis is the process of analyzing the information needs of the end users, the organizational environment and any systems presently being used thereby developing the functional requirements of a system that can meet the needs of the users. Also, the requirements should be recorded in a document, email, user interface. The requirements documentation should be referred to throughout the rest of the system development process to ensure the developing project aligns with the needs and requirements.

Design of a System:-

After the requirements have been determined, the necessary specification for the hardware, software, people, data resources, and the information products that will satisfy the functional requirements of the proposed system can be determined. The design will serve as a blue print for the systems and helps to detect these

problems before these errors or problems are built into the final system.

Development of Software:-

Coding and debugging is the act of creating the final system. Software developed may use purchased software or they may create new custom designed programs depending upon the cost and time available. Documentation is essential to test the program and carry out maintenance.

System Testing:-

The system must be tested to evaluate its actual functionality. In relation to expected or intended functionality. Some other issues to consider during this stage would be converting old data into the new system and training employees to use the new system. End users will be key in determining whether developed system meets the intended requirements, and the extent to which the system is actually used.

5.2 Hardware Requirement

- Display drive that should support 32-bit color scheme.
- Display resolution that should be 1024 x 768 pixels.
- Graphics Drive that can support 800 x 600 display resolution.
- Minimum of 128 MB RAM is required.
- The processor preferably should be Pentium III or above /its equivalent.

Justification

- The screen resolution of 1024 x 768 pixels must be used for the better vision and clarity of the system.
- Minimum 128 MB RAM must be used for faster access of the system.
- Processor of Pentium III or equivalent must be used for faster access of the system.

5.3 Software Requirement

- JDK 1.5
- Any Version of Windows, Macintosh, UNIX and Solaris.

Justification

- Since this application is developed using Java and full care is taken while coding to keep it platform independent.

5.4 Design issues of the procedure & algorithms:

The following considerations were made during the project.

- The data structure used to store the image data & encoding data is integer arrays.
- The image after it is watermarked is saved as the format with the same as the host image.
- The watermark insertion algorithm is minimally implemented with the least resistance to any attack.
- The watermark extraction algorithm is the reversal of the insertion algorithm.
- A simple spatial watermarking algorithm LSB is used.

5.4.1 The LSB Technique:

The LSB technique is the simplest technique of watermark insertion. If we specifically consider still images, each pixel of color image has four components -alpha, red, green & blue. Let us assume we allocate 4 bytes for each pixel. Thus, each color has 1 byte, or 8 bits, in which the intensity of that color can be specified on a scale of 0 to 255.

So a pixel that is bright purple in color would have full intensities of red & blue, but no green. Thus, that pixel can be shown as

$X0 = \{R=255, G=255, B=255\}$

Now, let's have a look at another pixel.

$X0 = \{R=254, G=254, B=254\}$

Now, since each color is stored in a separate byte, the last bit in each byte stores this difference in one. That is, the difference between values 255 & 254 is stored in the last bit, called Least Significant Bit.

Even after changing the value of RGB here, the difference is not noticeable to a human eye. For the eye, detecting a difference of 1 on a color scale of 256 is almost impossible.

5.4.2 Modified LSB algorithm:

A modification of the above method would be to use a secret key to choose a random location & replace the last bit with the watermark information. This technique of watermarking is invisible, as changes are made to the LSB only, but is not robust. Image manipulations, such as resampling, format conversion & cropping will in most cases result in watermarking information being lost. Let W be watermarking information. For every random pixel in the image, X_i

Do loop:

 Store the next bit from W in the LSB position of X_i (blue) byte.

End loop

To extract watermark information, we would simply need to take all the data in the LSBs in the same random sequence of the pixel and combine them.

5.5 Watermark embedding and extraction:

1. Informed(no oblivious or private)Watermarking.

Fig. 1 Watermark embedding process

Fig. 2 Watermark extraction process

2. Blind (oblivious or public) Watermarking.

Fig. 1 Watermark embedding process

Fig. 2 Watermark extraction process

6. Cost Benefit Analysis

Cost Benefit Analysis

For any given set of requirements by the user it is essential to know how much it will cost to develop the software to satisfy the given requirements, and how much time will be taken in the development process. These all estimates are required before development is initiated. The primary reason for cost and schedule estimation is to enable the client or developer to perform a cost-benefit analysis and for project monitoring and control.

The cost estimates are made at the planning phase of the project. Here in the planning phase we calculated the cost of this project using the COCOMO model. As per the calculations the total cost of the project is 8.0 persons month (PM).

6.1 Benefit Analysis

- The system provides a very good user-friendly interface to enhance the communication between the user and the software.
- The system is platform independent, thus allows the user to deploy on any operating system.
- The information security provided by this application is very valuable as any organization cannot compromise on this aspect.
- This application also provides the feature of transferring the files from one machine to another machine which is also the valuable aspect when combined with the security.
- This application also provide a very good help support for the application.

7. System life cycle

7.1 Description:

1) System Flow Chart

A flowchart is a picture of the separate steps of a process in sequential order. Elements that may be included are: sequence of actions, materials or services entering or leaving the process (inputs and outputs), decisions that must be made, people who become involved, time involved at each step and/or process measurements.

The process described can be anything: a manufacturing process, an administrative or service process, a project plan. This is a generic tool that can be adapted for a wide variety of purposes.

Commonly used symbols for flow chart are:

	<p>One step in the process; the step is written inside the box. Usually, only one arrow goes out of the box.</p>
	<p>Direction of flow from one step or decision to another.</p>
	<p>Decision based on a question. The question is written in the diamond. More than one arrow goes out of the diamond, each one showing the direction the process takes for a given answer to the question. (Often the answers are “yes” and “no.”)</p>
	<p>Delay or wait</p>
	<p>Link to another page or another flowchart. The same symbol on the other page indicates that the flow continues there.</p>
	<p>Input or output</p>
	<p>Document</p>
	<p>Alternate symbols for start and end points.</p>

SYSTEM FLOW CHART

8. Testing

The basic goal of software development process is to produce the software that has very few or no errors. In an effort to detect errors soon after they are introduced each phase ends with verification activity such as reviews. However most of these verification activities in the early phase of the software development are based on human evaluation and cannot detect all the errors. Testing plays an important role in quality assurance for the software. It is a dynamic method for the verification and validation, where the system to be tested is executed and the behavior of the system is observed.

8.1 Levels of testing

The programs are tested at various levels:

Unit testing

The first level of testing is called unit testing. In this different modules are tested against the specifications produced during design for the modules. Unit testing is essentially for verification of code produced during the coding phase and hence the goal is to test internal logic of the modules. Each of the modules is tested independently.

Integration testing

The next level of testing is often called integration testing. In this many unit tested modules are combined into sub systems which are then tested. The goal here is to see if the modules can be integrated properly.

System testing

This is the next levels of testing. Here the entire software is tested. The reference document for this process is the requirements document and the goal is to see if the software meets its requirements. This is essentially a validation exercise and in this situation it is the only validation activity.

8.2 Test Plan

A test plan is a general document for the entire project that defines the scope, approach to be taken, and the schedule of testing as well as identifies the test items for the entire testing process and the personnel responsible for the different activities of testing.

The test planning can be done well before the actual testing commences and can be done in parallel in the design and coding phase.

The input for the test plan is:

- 1) Project Plan
- 2) Requirement Document and
- 3) System Design Document.

The project plan is needed to make sure that the test plan can be consistent with the overall plan for the project and the testing schedule matches that of the project plan.

The requirement documents and the design document are the basic documents used for selecting the test unit and the deciding the approaches to be used during testing.

A test plan should contain following:

- 1) Test Unit Specification.
- 2) Features to be tested.
- 3) Approach for testing.

1) Test Unit

A test unit is a set of one or more modules, together with associated data, that are from a single computer program and that are the object of testing.

A test unit can occur at any level and can contain from a single module to the entire system.

2) Features to be tested.

All functional features specified in the requirement document will be tested. The features to be tested are:

- 1) Login
- 2) Embed Message
- 3) Embed File
- 4) Retrieve Message
- 5) Retrieve File
- 6) Send File and Message
- 7) Help

3) Approach for testing.

There are two approaches to testing:

1. Functional (Black Box) Testing

In functional testing the internal logic of the system is not considered and the test cases are decided from the specifications or the requirements. It is often called “Black Box” testing.

Test case 1: Login In

- After entering the user id and password when user will click on OK button, the application will check whether the user id and password is correct or not.
- If the user id and password is not correct then the application will show message that “Improper User Id Or Password”. At this point the text field where the user has entered the details will get deleted and user has to enter the details again.
- If the user id and password is correct then, the user will successfully login. After the successfully login application will show message “You have successfully logged in”.
- As soon as the user logs in with correct user id and password, all the buttons will get enabled and the user will get access the whole application.
- Either of the fields should not be left blank. If any of the field is left blank then it will show an alert message.

Test case 2: Embed Message

- User can embed the message behind the image, audio, and video. For that user has to enter the Input file and the message which is to be embedded.
- If the Embed process is successful then it will show message, “Embed Process completed Successfully”. If at all the embed process do not complete successfully, then it will generate an alert.
- As soon as the embed process complete successfully, the send button will get enabled and then the user can send the message to the desired destination.
- Either of the fields should not be left blank. If any of the field is left blank then it will show an alert message.

Test case 3: Embed File

- User can embed the entire file behind the image, audio, and video. For that user has to enter the Input file and the file that contains the data which is to be embedded.
- If the Embed process is successful then it will show message, “Embed Process completed Successfully”. If at all the embed process do not complete successfully, then it will generate an alert.

- As soon as the embed process complete successfully, the send button will get enabled and then the user can send the message to the desired destination.
- Either of the fields should not be left blank. If any of the field is left blank then it will show an alert message.

Test case 4: Retrieve Message

- User can retrieve the entire message from the image, audio, and video. For that user has to enter the Input file in which the message has been embedded. Then user has to click on retrieve button to get the content.
- If the Retrieve process is successful then it will show message, “Retrieve Process completed Successfully”. If at all the retrieve process do not complete successfully, then it will generate an alert.
- If the retrieve process completes successfully, then the message, which was embedded, will get visible in the text area provided for displaying the message.
- As soon as the retrieve process complete successfully, the save button will get enabled and then the user can save the message to the desired location.
- Either of the fields should not be left blank. If any of the field is left blank then it will show an alert message.

Test case 5: Retrieve File

- User can retrieve the entire file from the image, audio, and video. For that user has to enter the Input file in which the file has been embedded. Then user has to click on retrieve button.
- If the Retrieve process is successful then it will show message, “Retrieve Process completed Successfully”. If at all the retrieve process do not complete successfully, then it will generate an alert.
- If the retrieve process completes successfully, then the file, which was embedded, will first ask for the location to get stored. After storing the message the user can see the content of the file by opening it.
- Either of the fields should not be left blank. If any of the field is left blank then it will show an alert message.

Test case 6: Send File

- User can send message to the desired destination by entering the destination name or address.
- If the user enters the wrong destination name or address then it will show alert message.

- After entering the destination name and address user has to click on send button.
- If the receiver accepts the file then it will show message to sender that file has been accepted.
- If receiver rejects the file then it will show message that file has been rejected.
- If any of the field is left blank then it will show an alert message.

Test Case 7: Help File

- User when goes to the Help menu and clicks on Help button then Help window get open.
- Help window also get displayed when user presses Shif+F1.
- On clicking on the hyperlinks in the help window the desired page is displayed in the window.
- Clicking on the back hyperlink on the help page main help menu is displayed

2. Structural (White Box) Testing

In structural testing, the test cases are decided entirely on the internal logic of the program or module being tested. The external specifications are not considered.

In white box testing we check

- Whether all the methods are implemented and working properly.
- All the conditional statement is giving right output or not.
- Whether the variable that is declared is reserved or not and also checked the scope of variable.
- Whether all the control properties are used appropriately.
- Proper validation of various fields is done or not.

Test case 1:

- Whether the user name and password is correct or not. If the user name and password is not correct then it will show message that message has been not entered properly. If the user name and password is correct then the user will get access to the application.

Test case 2:

- Whether all the buttons become enabled after the successful login. Some of the buttons which are required for accessing the application will get enabled only if the user enters proper user name and password.

Test case 3:

- Whether the message is entered in text area or not. If message is not provided in text area, then it will ask user to enter the message.

Test case 4:

- Whether the selected input file is valid or not. That is, the input file which is selected should be present in the system and also it should be valid.

Test case 5:

- Whether the embed process complete successfully or not. If the embed process do not complete successfully then it will shoe error message. If the embed process complete successfully then it will then it will give message that the embed process has been completed successfully.

Test case 6:

- Whether the connection is established between the sender or receiver or not.

Test case 7:

- Whether the message or the file reaches the destination successfully or not. If the file or message do not reach destination, then it will show an message. If he file or message reaches the destination then it will show message that the send process completed successfully.

Test case 8:

- Whether the message or the file has been received by the receiver or not. If the receiver does not accept the file sent by the sender, then it will show message to the sender that the file has been rejected. If the message or the file is accepted by the receiver then it will show message to the user that file has been accepted.

Test case 9:

- Whether the retrieve operation can fetch the message or file or not. If the retrieve operation fail to retrieve the message or file then it will display the message. If the retrieve operation complete successfully the then it will ask the receiver to set the location for the file to be saved. Similarly the message which is retrieved can also be saved.

Test case 10:

- Whether the destination address is proper or not. That means the address which is entered should exist in the intra net environment. If the destination machine is not in the intra net environment then it will give message to the user that path not found.

Test case 11:

- Whether the input file from which the user is trying to fetch result contain embedded message or not. If the input file do not contain embedded message then it will show error message.

9. Limitation and Future enhancement

9.1 Limitation of the project:

1. The application cannot have multiple login id and password.
2. If any one makes changes in log file then it security is lost.
3. The application cannot embed message in text file. If it tries to embed message in text file then it will show distorted text file.
4. Only text file can be embedded in image, audio and video file. No other files can be embedded.
5. The message cannot be transferred to any other device such as mobile.
6. The message can be transferred in intranet environment and not in Internet environment.
7. The content of the file cannot be seen in the text area provided for displaying the message.

9.2 Future Enhancement:

1. The application can have multiple login id and password.
2. Security will not lose by any mean.
3. The application can embed message in text file.
4. Not only text file but also any other file can be embedded in image, audio and video file.
5. The message can be transferred in intranet and in Internet environment.
6. The message can be transferred to any other device such as mobile.
7. The content of the file can be seen in the text area provided for displaying the messages.

Citations

1. Acharya, Kamal, Attendance Management System Project (April 28, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4810251> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4810251>
2. Acharya, Kamal, Online Food Order System (May 2, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4814732> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4814732>
3. Acharya, Kamal, University management system project. (May 1, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4814103> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4814103>
4. Acharya, Kamal, Online banking management system. (May 1, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4813597> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4813597>
5. Acharya, Kamal, Online Job Portal Management System (May 5, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4817534> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4817534>
6. Acharya, Kamal, Employee leave management system. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819626> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819626>
7. Acharya, Kamal, Online electricity billing project report. (May 7, 2024). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4819630> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4819630>
8. Acharya, Kamal, POLICY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM PROJECT REPORT. (December 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831694> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831694>
9. Acharya, Kamal, Online job placement system project report. (January 10, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831638> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831638>
10. Acharya, Kamal, Software testing for project report. (May 16, 2023). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831028> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831028>
11. Acharya, Kamal, ONLINE CRIME REPORTING SYSTEM PROJECT. (August 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4831015> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831015>
12. Acharya, Kamal, Burger ordering system project report. (October 10, 2022). Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4832704> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4832704>

References

1. Cox, I. J., Miller, M. L., Bloom, J. A., Fridrich, J., & Kalker, T. (2008). *Digital watermarking and steganography* (2nd ed.). Morgan Kaufmann.
2. Katzenbeisser, S., & Petitcolas, F. A. P. (2000). *Information hiding techniques for steganography and digital watermarking*. Artech House.
3. Wolfgang, R. B., & Delp, E. J. (2002). *Techniques and applications of digital watermarking and content protection*. CRC Press.